

Economic burden of podiatric care for diabetic foot ulcers in the Czech Republic: A prospective multicenter study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Diabetic foot (DF), especially DF ulcers (DFUs) are a relatively frequent and financially burdensome late-stage complication of diabetes. However, data on the costs of podiatric care in the Czech Republic are scarce. The aim of this prospective multicenter study was to determine the total costs associated with long-term podiatric care in selected foot clinics across the Czech Republic.

Research Design and Methods: A total of 119 patients with DFUs (mean age of 68 ± 11 years, diabetes duration of 19 ± 11 years, HbA1c level of 62 ± 14 mmol/mol, composite Wifl score of 3 ± 2 , 33 % had new DFUs, 37 % previous amputations, and 50 % had peripheral artery disease (PAD)) from 10 podiatric foot clinics in the Czech Republic were enrolled in our financial analysis. Direct and indirect costs associated with podiatric care – diagnostic and treatment methods – including angiological, radiological, and microbiological examinations, blood sampling, prescribed materials for local therapy, antibiotics, surgical procedures, offloading devices, hospital services and additional expenses such as patient transportation, doctors' visits, home care assistance, and work incapacity – were monitored over a 6-month period using an electronic database.

Results: The average cost of podiatric care per patient over a 6-month period was €2,506 with median €1,320. The largest expenses were spent on therapeutic procedures (51.4 %). Costs for patients hospitalized during the study period were significantly higher than for outpatients (€7,923 vs. €1,304 on average; $P < 0.001$). Among hospitalized patients, the main costs were hospital services (32 %), therapeutic procedures (26 %), and antibiotic and local therapies (20 %). Among outpatients, therapeutic procedures accounted for 74 % of the total costs. Newly developed DFUs or PAD were not linked to significantly increased costs. The composite Wifl score, primarily the wound component, was the only parameter that significantly positively correlated with the total podiatric costs ($r = 0.434$; 95 % CI 0.279–0.559; $P < 0.0001$). Other patient characteristics such as age, diabetes duration, DFU duration, and HbA1c level did not show significant cost correlations.

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Conclusions: On average, podiatric care for patients with DFUs in the Czech Republic is 3 to 9 times more expensive than standard diabetes healthcare. The expenses for hospitalized patients are almost 6 times higher than for outpatients. The composite Wifl score was the most significant indicator of podiatric financial burden.

1. Introduction

Diabetic foot syndrome (DFS) is a late-stage complication of diabetes. Occurrence of DFS varies globally, even among European countries [1]. The prevalence of DFS ranges from 1.5 to 16.6 % in diabetic populations across Europe [1] and is estimated at around 6.3 % globally [1].

While comprehensive treatment of DFS, involving local wound care, offloading, vascular interventions, and infection management, is essential, it is also financially burdensome. Despite its significance, economic data on DFS management are scarce. However, the available studies highlight substantial disparities in treatment costs and outcomes across different regions. The cost related to DFS and amputation extended to \$33 500 per patient in the UK, US and other high income European countries, those related to DFU not requiring amputation were \$17 500. Globally, economic studies described a steep increase in DFS related expenses in high income countries over the last 20 years [3]. Compared to these expenditures, they are lower in middle-income countries due to insufficient available options for treatment [3].

In the Czech Republic, over 7 % of diabetes patients are affected by DFS, according to the Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic [2]. We suppose that the costs dedicated to podiatric care are much higher in contrast to total financial demands spent on diabetes management in our country. However, data on the financial burden of podiatric care in the Czech Republic, essential for informing government policies and insurance companies to change their

healthcare policy, is currently lacking. Only hard data on economic costs obtained from podiatric clinical practice can help change the real situation, which is currently unsatisfied. Only systemic transformation can reduce these financial expenditures since only widely and timely accessible podiatric care is able to prevent the development of DFS. Therefore the aim of this prospective multicenter study was to quantify the direct and indirect costs associated with long-term podiatric care in selected foot clinics across the country. This involved determining the total cost of podiatric care, comparing the costs of care for hospitalized and outpatient patients, and assessing whether total costs are higher for newly enrolled patients with foot lesions or for those with peripheral ischemia.

2. Research Design and methods

2.1. Study Design

A total of 119 patients with DFUs from 10 podiatric foot clinics in the Czech Republic (Fig. 1) were enrolled in our financial analysis. The patients had a mean age of 68 ± 11 years, diabetes duration of 19 ± 11 years, HbA1c level of 62 ± 14 mmol/mol, and composite Society for Vascular Surgery Wound, Ischemia, and foot Infection (Wifl) score of 3 ± 2 . Of these patients, 33 % had new DFUs, 37 % had previous amputations, and 50 % had peripheral artery disease (PAD) (Tables 1-3).

This prospective analysis was part of a traditional internal audit conducted every second year by the Podiatric Section of Czech Diabetes

Fig. 1. Map of the Czech Republic showing the distribution of podiatry clinics incorporated into the study. List of centers in alphabetical order: Department of Internal Medicine, Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague; Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague; Diabetes Centre, Department of Internal Medicine, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University and Military University Hospital, Prague; Diabetology and Podiatry Outpatient Clinic, Dr Pírek Clinic, Mladá Boleslav; Diabetology and Podiatry Clinic, Vratimov; Diabetology and Podiatry Outpatient Clinic, Příbram Regional Hospital, Příbram; Department of Internal Medicine and Cardiology, Ostrava University Hospital, Ostrava; Salvatella Outpatient Clinic, Trinec; Diabetology and Nutrition Centre, First Department of Internal Medicine, Plzeň University Hospital, Plzeň; Third Clinic of Internal Medicine Clinic, Department of Endocrinology and Metabolism, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University and General University Hospital, Prague.

Table 1
Basal characteristics of patients with DFUs enrolled in the study.

Evaluated parameters	All patients (n = 119)	Hospitalized patients (n = 23)	Outpatients (n = 96)
Age (years)	68 ± 11	69 ± 10	67 ± 11
Diabetes duration (years)	19 ± 11	21 ± 10	19 ± 11
Type 1 diabetes / Type 2 diabetes / Other types of diabetes (%)	6 / 89 / 5	5 / 85 / 10	7 / 90 / 3
HbA1c (mmol/mol ⁻¹)	62 ± 14	65 ± 14	62 ± 14
BMI (kg/m ⁻²)	32 ± 6	33 ± 8	32 ± 6
New patients with DFUs (%)	33	48	28
PAD (%)	50	74	42
Stroke (%)	16	13	16
CAD (%)	38	43	35
Diabetic retinopathy (%)	50	65	46
DKD (%)	96	91	97
CKD (%)	54	52	56
Transplant patients (%)	1	4	0

HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; BMI, body mass index; DFU, diabetic foot ulcer; PAD, peripheral artery disease; CAD, coronary artery disease; DKD, diabetic kidney disease; CKD, chronic kidney disease; n, number.

Table 2
Basal podiatric characteristics of patients enrolled in the study.

Evaluated parameters	All patients (n = 119)	Hospitalized patients (n = 23)	Outpatients (n = 96)
DFU duration (months)	9 ± 17	5 ± 6	10 ± 19
Composite Wifl score	3 ± 2	5 ± 2	3 ± 2
Previous amputation (%)	37	30	37

DFU, diabetic foot ulcer; Wifl, Wound, Ischemia, and foot Infection; n, number.

Table 3
Socioeconomic status of patients.

Evaluated parameters	All patients (n = 119)	Hospitalized patients (n = 23)	Outpatients (n = 96)
Fully employed (%)	16.3	13	17.8
Unemployed (%)	2.6	8.7	1.1
Partial invalidity pension (%)	7.8	0	10
Full invalidity pension (%)	9.5	17.4	7.8
Retirement pension (%)	63.8	60.9	63.3
Mean 1-month financial loss per patient (€) – mean 1-year financial loss per patient (€)	27 ± 117–323	79 ± 227–949	15 ± 67–180
Care allowance (%)	24.4	36.8	19.3

n, number; €, euro.

Society across all registered foot clinics nationwide. All consecutively treated patients with DFUs, including new referrals to podiatric clinics, were enrolled in the study. A maximum of 30 participants per clinic was set. Patients were followed and treated by their podiatrist or diabetologist for 6 months. During the follow up period, these patients were treated in out-patient or even in hospitalization mode, if it was necessary. Patients with a life expectancy of less than 6 months, those unable to cooperate with the provision of data describing health or economic status or their patient history or those not attending regularly foot clinics, or those transferred to other clinics were excluded. All participants signed their informed consents approved by appropriate hospitals or foot clinics following patients.

2.2. System of podiatric care in Czech republic

There exist 40 registered and approved outpatient foot clinics of intermediate and advanced type of podiatric care. Nearly half of them work as ambulances connected to the departments of Internal Medicine or Diabetes centres. The rest of podiatric foot clinics form parts of outpatients diabetes ambulances. As the outpatient as hospital podiatric care is nearly completely covered by insurance companies via performance payment (in outpatient sector) and DRG system (hospital stay). Podiatric patients participate during payment on only minimum of items – predominantly dressing materials or selected drugs.

2.3. Data Collection

Direct costs associated with diagnostic and treatment methods – including angiological, radiological and microbiological examinations, blood tests, local wound care materials, antibiotics, surgical procedures, offloading devices and further expenditures (indirect costs) were monitored over a 6-month period using an electronic database. We have focused during the indirect expenditure analysis on the costs connected to the other medical specialists' visits, home care assistants and their services, patient transportation to foot clinics. Also, we have counted work incapacity and potential money lost of these study subjects due to illness and not receiving their standard salaries. All mentioned items were discussed with each study subject during each visit, counted and included into the final statistical analysis.

The total financial burden of hospitalizations was counted as costs spent on hospital services (hotel services) and performed diagnostic and therapeutic procedures. All items were counted separately based on recent prices for selected hospital where study subject has been admitted.

Our IT specialists based on google spreadsheets application, to which main author, coauthors and statisticians only had open access, built up this database. The collected data were subsequently analyzed statistically.

Patients were divided into two main groups: outpatients treated exclusively in a clinic setting and inpatients hospitalized at least once during follow-up period. Statistical analysis was also performed separately for newly referred patients with DFUs and those suffering from PAD.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Results are presented as means ± standard deviations and with 95 % confidence intervals (CI) for means, or as medians with quartiles for continuous variables. Discrete variables are presented as counts and percentages. Given the non-normal distribution of cost data (heavily right-skewed), nonparametric statistical methods were employed. The Wilcoxon rank sum test was used for between-group comparisons, Spearman's rank correlation for associations between variables, and bootstrapping to construct confidence intervals.

All tests were two-sided, and a *P* value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. *P* values and confidence intervals are reported without multiple testing corrections. Statistical analysis was performed using R version 4.3.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

3. Results

The average cost of podiatric care was €2,506 ± €3,578 per patient over a 6-month period (95 % CI €2,005 – €3,243), with a median of €1,321. The largest cost components were therapeutic procedures (51.4 %) and hospital hotel services (17.3 %) (Fig. 2 and Table 4). Patients hospitalized during the study period incurred significantly higher costs than outpatients (€7,923 ± €5,572 vs. €1,304 ± €1,169; *P* < 0.001; Table 5). For hospitalized patients, the main expenses were hospital

Fig. 2. Distribution of Czech healthcare costs for diabetic foot care broken down into 5 key categories: therapy (51.41%), hospital services (17.33%), indirect costs (14.18%), routine clinical services (7.53%) and diagnostic procedures (9.60%).

Table 4

Total costs of podiatric care for all patients over a 6-month period.

Evaluated parameters	Total costs (%)	Mean cost (€) ± SD (€)	95 % CI (min – max)	Median (€)
Total costs	100	2,506 ± 3,578	2,005–3,243	1,321
Therapy	51.4	1,288 ± 1,795	1,042–1,671	762
Hospital services	17.3	434 ± 1,437	244–759	0
Other costs	14.2	355 ± 676	257–496	47
Diagnostic procedures	9.6	239 ± 380	183–315	83
Routine clinical services	7.5	188 ± 114	171–209	169

€, euro; CI, confidence interval.

services (33 %), therapeutic procedures (26 %), and antibiotic and other drugs (20 %). For outpatients, therapeutic procedures accounted for 74 % of the total costs (Table 5). Costs for patients with newly developed DFUs or PAD were not significantly higher than those for patients without these conditions (Figs. 3 and 4).

Among the parameters evaluated, including patient and DFU characteristics such as age, diabetes or DFU duration, HbA1c, and composite Wifl score, only the composite Wifl score – particularly the wound component (Fig. 5) – significantly positively correlated with total podiatric costs ($r = 0.434$; 95 % CI 0.279–0.559; $P < 0.0001$). The other

patient or DFU characteristics did not significantly correlate with podiatric financial demands.

4. Discussion

DFS is a relatively frequent late-stage complication of diabetes mellitus. A large meta-analysis estimated a global DF incidence of approximately 6.3 % from the total diabetic cohort, with higher rates in men, individuals with type 2 diabetes, older patients (mean age 55–70), and those with longer disease duration [1]. As the elderly population grows and comorbidities increase, the cost of DF, especially of DFUs treatment is expected to rise. Financial demands for DFU care are influenced not only by the duration and severity of diabetes [4,5], but also by the increasing prevalence of DFUs and their associated complications.

Our prospective study revealed a substantial economic burden associated with podiatric care. The total cost per patient over a 6-month period was approximately €2,500, with considerable variation. While we calculated the direct and indirect costs of DFUs management, we did not include the costs of diabetes treatment itself. According to annual reports from Czech insurance companies, the annual cost of diabetes management typically ranges from €600 to €1,800. Given that over 7 % of diabetes patients in the Czech Republic develop DF [2], podiatric care represents a significant financial burden on the healthcare system. This burden is far from a minor component of the diabetes management budget, amounting to an estimated €350 million annually.

Table 5

Comparison of costs between podiatric hospitalized patients and outpatients over a 6-month period.

Evaluated parameters	Hospitalized patients (n = 23)				Outpatients (n = 96)				P value
	Total costs (%)	Mean cost (€) ± SD (€)	95 % CI (min – max)	Median (€)	Total costs (%)	Mean cost (€) ± SD (€)	95 % CI (min – max)	Median (€)	
Total costs	100	7,923 ± 5,572	6,008–10,561	6,128	100	1,304 ± 1,169	1,081–1,551	1,115	<0.001
Hospital services	33	2,512 ± 2,632	1,672–3,847	1,862	0	0	0	0	Not relevant
Diagnostic procedures	10	804 ± 587	582–1,047	800	8	107 ± 140	81–138	62	<0.001
Therapy	26	2,085 ± 1,919	1,543–3,319	1,764	74	966 ± 929	790–1,164	692	<0.001
Antibiotics and other drugs	20	1,579 ± 1,876	1,006–2,614	901	1	11 ± 17	8–15	0	<0.001
Other costs	10	831 ± 963	496–1,273	162	17	220 ± 490	130–326	0	<0.001
Transportation	1	111 ± 51	88–125	107	0	0	0	0	<0.001

n, number; €, euro; CI, confidence interval.

Fig. 3. Comparison of total podiatric care costs for chronic versus newly developed DFUs ($P = 0.24$). All data points are plotted alongside box plots showing the median cost (bold horizontal line), the interquartile range (box), and the range without outliers (vertical line segments).

Many studies focus on the broader financial implications of podiatric care at a national or international level [6]. Some studies consider only direct costs [7], while others include both direct and indirect costs [8]. Comparisons have even been made between podiatric care and other costly conditions, such as cancer [7]. For example, Armstrong et al. reported that in 2017 the annual direct cost of diabetes care in the US was \$237 billion, a 26 % increase from 2012 [7]. This figure was nearly triple the cost of cancer management. Notably, approximately one-third of these diabetes care costs were attributed to lower extremity complications [7].

A large UK study estimated the annual cost of podiatric care for patients with DFUs and amputations in 2014 and 2015 at £837 million and £962 million, respectively, accounting for 0.8 to 0.9 % of the National Health Service budget [9]. Over 90 % of these costs were associated with DFUs [9], with expenditure increasing with long-term therapy, disease severity, and recurrent ulcers [9]. The authors concluded that the cost of diabetic foot care in the UK exceeds the combined cost of breast, prostate and lung cancer care. Another study suggested that DFUs incur annual costs of \$9 to \$13 billion for the

Fig. 4. Comparison of total podiatric costs for patients with ischemic versus nonischemic DFUs ($P = 0.53$). All data points are plotted alongside box plots showing the median cost (bold horizontal line), the interquartile range (box), and the range without outliers (vertical line segments).

Medicare health insurance program in the US, with the highest expenses associated with infected lesions, primarily due to inpatient care and hospital admissions [4].

Most studies estimate total expenditure on DFS or DFUs, but in our prospective study, we adopted a different approach. By relating costs to individual patients, we better reflect the specific severity of each case in relation to DFU severity or complications. Our study focused on patients who were either known to be ischemic or had newly developed DFUs. The individual costs averaged €2,500, with a median of €1,320 over 6 months. In contrast, a methodological review by Schirr-Bonnans reported an annual average cost of \$10,604 (ranging from \$1,444 to \$85,718 described in the manuscripts published between 2000 and 2015), which is nearly triple our findings [6]. However, this was a review and analyze of 44 published papers from originally preselected 9049 manuscripts that passed inclusion and exclusion criteria for study selection.

Our prospective study is unique in that we collected data continuously and individually, rather than anonymously from insurance companies sources or databases, which are subject to large biases and high

Fig. 5. Scatter plot showing a positive correlation between the composite Wifl score and total podiatric costs. All data points are plotted along with a linear regression line. The shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval, indicating that any regression line fitting within this region is statistically admissible.

error rates. By focusing on individual patient costs, we were able to provide a more accurate representation of real-world costs, minimizing potential biases and errors inherent in aggregated data.

An intriguing study by Tcherro et al. mapped the costs for patients with DFUs across 5 countries: France, Spain, Italy, Germany, and the UK. The total cost of amputation varied significantly over time, ranging from \$15,046 in 2001 to \$38,621 in 2005. Direct amputation costs fluctuated even more dramatically, from \$13,842 in 2001 to \$83,728 between 2005 and 2009. In contrast, indirect costs were more uniform, ranging from \$1,043 to \$1,442. Gangrene accounted for approximately one-fifth of the total cost [10], with considerable variation across countries. Similar to our data, noninfected ulcers were less financially burdensome than infected ulcers [10]. Note, however, that this study was a review of existing literature and limited to the podiatric care economy, analyzing only 9 studies from an initial pool of 1,340 manuscripts.

All of these expenses could be significantly reduced due to sophisticated prevention programs and multidisciplinary podiatric approach that would be able to reduce the occurrence of DFUs and DFS based on extensive podiatric screening and preventive podiatric programs or decreased DFS complications via comprehensive podiatric care performed by multidisciplinary teams [11].

The focus of our study was on analyzing the individual cost components associated with DFUs management. We found that the largest expenses were incurred for therapy procedures, hospital services, and antibiotic therapy. Hospitalized patients incurred significantly higher costs (approximately 6 times more) than outpatients during follow-up, with hospital hotel services, therapeutic procedures, antibiotics, being the primary drivers of expense. For outpatients, therapeutic procedures accounted for the majority of the financial burden. Specifically, local therapy, antibiotics, offloading devices, rehabilitation, specialist consultations, and minor surgical procedures comprised nearly three-quarters of the total cost for outpatients. These findings align with the Eurodiale study, where an analysis of more than 800 patients with DFUs found that hospitalization, antibiotics, amputations, and other surgeries were the highest costs per patient [12]. Another study reported that, according to multiple regression analysis, DFUs costs were primarily associated with the length of hospital stay [9]. Our study did not prove such associations.

We hypothesized that certain patient characteristics, particularly new occurrence of DFU or its severity and the presence of PAD, might influence the total financial demands of podiatric care for DFUs patients in the Czech Republic. Surprisingly, however, patients with newly

developed DFUs or PAD did not incur significantly higher costs than those without these conditions. This contrasts with findings from the Eurodiale study, where total expenditure per patient was over 4 times higher for those with infection and PAD at inclusion into observation trial compared to those in the least severe group without these conditions [8].

While there are limited data on the specific costs associated with newly developed ulcers, our study provides valuable insights into this area. Infectious DFUs complications likely contribute more to the economic burden of podiatric care than PAD. Estimates suggest that 40 to 80 % of DFUs become infected, and these are the primary cause of hospitalizations in patients with DFUs [4]. According to Geraghty et al., the most significant costs associated with DFUs are inpatient expenses and hospital admissions [4]. This is likely due to the extended hospital stays and the need for increased hospital services and antibiotic treatments, as evidenced by our findings. Similarly, Hicks et al. found that hospital costs per DFU admission were significantly higher for infected cases than for other causes (\$11,290 vs. \$8,145) [5].

Our results indicate that DFU severity, as classified by the Wifl staging system, particularly in relation to infection, can impact total financial expenditure for podiatric care. Interestingly, wound characteristics seem to be the most significant factor contributing to economic burden, followed by infection and PAD. Consistent with these findings, several studies have reported that all types of resource utilization and costs increase with DFU severity [4,8]. Additionally, the chronicity of the illness, the recurrence of podiatric problems [12], and complications leading to lower limb amputations may raise costs further. In our study, other patient characteristics did not appear to have a substantial impact on economic outcomes.

In this context, early detection of patients at risk of DFUs is crucial for reducing the overall cost of podiatric care. In the Czech Republic, this can be achieved by expanding the number of foot clinics, thus increasing the capacity for preventive care, and strengthening collaboration between podiatrists and primary care providers, such as general practitioners, diabetologists, and specialized pedicurists. Only these approaches will ensure a significant decrease in the substantial costs associated with podiatric care for patients with DFUs in our country. By adhering to best practice treatment protocols based on national recommendations and international guidelines, we can significantly lower all associated costs [13].

Our study is not without its limitations. We enrolled into our prospective study patients from only 10 podiatric centers in the Czech Republic, which may seem like an insufficient sample size. However, these centers account a quarter of the currently registered outpatient foot clinics in the country. All of participant foot clinics have enrolled a representative sample of consecutively treated patients with DFUs from their entire cohort of podiatric population. Therefore, we believe this analysis is representative and reflects the true economic landscape of podiatric care at the national level. Additionally, our data do not incorporate the final outcomes of podiatric care. In other words, our economic analysis does not focus primary on the healing of DFUs, amputations, or patient mortality. Instead, we aimed to provide an overview of clinical practice, offering healthcare professionals a framework for understanding the economic costs associated with patients newly referred to podiatric care due to a newly diagnosed ulcer or with ischemic patients, or those requiring imminent hospitalization for DFUs.

To conclude, podiatric care for patients with DFUs is 3 to 9 times more expensive than standard healthcare of diabetic subjects in the Czech Republic. Annually, it is estimated in total to €350 million. Hospitalized patients with DFUs incur significantly higher costs, approximately 6 times more than outpatients. This means that the costs are high by Czech standards, although the costs were attributed to patients with DFUs only, since the financial expenditure to Charcot foot and other pathologies is probably different due to diverse management of such pathology. Financial expenditures should be reduced by improving the availability of podiatric care. If a patient comes with more advanced

findings, i.e. a higher composite WIFI score, the costs of care will certainly proportionally increase, because the composite WIFI score is the only one significant indicator of the overall financial burden of podiatric care in our country.

Also, it is necessary to emphasize and put our effort to the early detection of DFU-risk patients. We will achieve this in our country by increasing the number of foot clinics that have sufficient capacity for preventive care. It would be appropriate to strengthen the cooperation of podiatrists with the first line of health care professionals, who will actively search for and care for patients at risk of DF. Pedicurists specialized in podiatry, general practitioners, other specialists and diabetologists themselves should be certainly involved. Only these approaches will further ensure a significant reduction of the enormous costs associated with podiatric care for patients with active DF in the Czech Republic. Because if we follow *lege artis* treatment according to national recommendations and international guidelines, we can extensively reduce all costs [13].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vladimíra Fejfarová: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Koliba:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pavlna Piřhová:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Milan Flekač:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Věra Prýmková:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Johana Venerová:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jan Stryja:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Martina Kořková:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Hana Kůsová:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jan Mareš:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Alexandra Jirkovská:** Writing – review & editing. **Jarmila Jirkovská:** Writing – review & editing. **Bedřich Sixta:** Writing – review & editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

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